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Robust Control of Positive 2-Dimensional Systems with Bounded Realness Property

Abstract: As presented in this paper, we explore the control of a discrete-time two-dimensional (2-D) system using the Lyapunov approach. The Giovane–Roesser model (G–R) for 2-D systems was introduced, and we presented the asymptotic stability analysis for this class of systems while maintaining the strictly bounded real (SBR) property. In the next step, we solve the stability problem in the presence of uncertainties in the system while preserving the SBR condition. We design state feedback and output feedback controllers to control 2-D discrete-time systems with preceding uncertainties, introducing algorithms to design such controllers. In order to ensure the validity of our findings, we present the simulation results as numerical and practical examples.

Keywords: Asymptotic stability, 2-D systems, Bounded realness, Robust stability, State feedback, Output feedback

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